

MECHANICAL TESTING OF ADHESIVELY JOINED SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Due to their specific bending stiffness, sandwich structures consisting of a foam core and face sheets made of fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) have gained importance in many industrial products, especially in the aerospace, shipbuilding and transportation industries. In order to utilize the full advantages of sandwich structures, one of the major challenges is the load application using proper joining techniques. Adhesive bonding has shown high potential as a possible joining technique. In order to be able to determine the applicability of adhesive bonding and joint configurations, suitable test methods have to be applied. There are plenty of standards to determine the mechanical properties of monolithic sandwich structures. However, it is still challenging to test the bonding strength of adhesively joined sandwiches as there are no standards available.

This study focuses on the development of test methods which allow an evaluation of adhesive bonds between two sandwich structures. Modifications of standardized tests for monolithic sandwich beams (three-point bending and four-point bending) are used to determine the strength of butt-joined sandwich structures and the advantages and disadvantages are discussed. In addition, techniques to test corner joints and T-joints are investigated.

The results of this study show that new test methods for butt-joint sandwich structures have to be developed as the existing test techniques are not suitable for testing joined sandwiches. Four-point bending is not a suitable experimental setup, as some of the joint sandwiches considered failed at the point of load application, due to indentation. It was shown that the failure mode is highly influenced by the core properties in these tests. The actual strength of the bond cannot be determined and therefore the test is not suitable. In three-point bending, the load is applied directly into the bonding area, whereby the design of the joint influences the test results directly. Furthermore, different techniques to test T-joints and corner joints were studied and evaluated regarding their suitability to test adhesively joined sandwich structures. The test methods used to examine T-joints and corner joints show good potential to test joined sandwich structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures consisting of a foam core and face sheets made of fiber-reinforced plastics offer many advantages compared to monolithic fiber-reinforced plastics (frp). These structures allow an enormous increase of bending stiffness and offer intrinsic features such as noise and heat insulation as well as enlarged impact resistance. Therefore these structures are widely used in modern lightweight constructions. However, there are still difficulties that have to be considered when using sandwich panels. One of these challenges is the joining process. Numerous joining techniques have been suggested based on adhesive bonding or mechanical joining. In order to evaluate and to optimize these joining techniques, mechanical testing or numerical simulations are used. Unfortunately, there are no standardized test methods for joined sandwich structures that allow a neutral comparison of different joining configurations and a definite statement concerning the mechanical properties of these joints. For these reasons, this study focuses on different techniques to test joined sandwich structures as well as their ability to evaluate the bending strength of joined sandwich structures.

2 STATE OF THE ART

2.1 Standardization in testing of sandwich structures

Sandwich structures are widely used and there are plenty of test standards for monolithic sandwich structures. Popular test standards are those of the “ASTM International” (formerly American Society for Testing and Materials, ASTM) or the “Deutsches Institut für Normung” (DIN). These test standards give instructions as to how to execute tests to determine basic properties of the different components as cores or adhesive bonds between the core and the faces as well as the bending properties of monolithic sandwich structures. Widely used standards to determine the tensile strength of the core, the core-to-facing bond, or the facing of an assembled sandwich panel are ASTM C297/C297M-15 [1] and DIN 53292 [2]. These standards give test instructions as to how a tensile test perpendicular to the faces has to be performed. Conversely, DIN 53291 [3] describes the experimental procedure to conduct a compression test perpendicular to the faces. There are also tests to determine the cleavage force to peel the faces from the core (e.g. DIN 53295 [4] or ASTM E2004-10 [5]). Another important value for sandwich elements is the shear strength, and there are several methods to evaluate this property, such as DIN 53294 [6] or ASTM C273/C273M-11 [7]. Besides these methods, bending tests can also determine basic properties, such as shear strength. There are two different techniques to subject a sandwich panel to a bending moment, i.e. three- and four-point bending. Both tests are also used to make statements concerning the bending properties of the assembled sandwiches. Thus, there is a wide range of test methods, but no specific standardized test method to evaluate the bending strength of adhesively joined sandwich structures.

2.2 Testing of adhesively joined sandwich structures

Within recent years, several test methods have been suggested to evaluate the properties of joined sandwich structures. In general, the studies focus on bending and tensile tests.

Methods for testing butt-joined sandwich structures focus on modified three-point and four-point bending tests. In [8] shear tests on short beams according to ASTM C393/C393M [9] on adhesively joined sandwich structures with different edging configurations were performed. It was shown that in all cases failure occurred far away from the joining zone.

For corner joints, [10] propose two different test setups for bending and shear testing. Within this study, different joint configurations were considered. For bending, a modified three-point bending test was applied. The shear test applied clamping on one side of the sandwich, while the second one was pulled out perpendicularly. The specimens failed either due to core failure or to bonding failure.

Most publications were made on T-joints focusing on tension tests [11-15]. The specimens were fixed to a test rig and the orthogonal beam was pulled out until failure occurred. In [16] a bending test was proposed.

Thus, many different studies were conducted on the testing of joined sandwich structures. However, an important fact has not been regarded within these studies. The applicability of the test techniques, especially the sensitivity of the test methods to evaluate the effect of construction design on the mechanical performance is not considered.

4 EXPERIMENTALS

Within this study, bending tests with different sandwich configurations were performed. First, monolithic as well as joined sandwich beams were tested in three-point bending and four-point bending. The influence of the joint as well as the suitability of the test methods is described. In addition, bending tests on T-joints and corner joints were performed, and the significance of the results concerning the influence of the joint is discussed.

4.1 Materials and specimen preparation

The sandwiches used in this study were manufactured at the institute of joining and welding so that the influence of the material properties on the test results could be determined. Based on these outcomes an evaluation of the testing methods was possible. The sandwiches consisted of different

Figure 2: Sketch of a joined specimen

Test series 1 had thick foam cores (25°mm) while series 2 had five times lower foam thicknesses. As the measurements of the specimens depend on their thickness, the specimens of series 2 are much smaller as those of series 1. The joined specimens had the same overall sizes as the monolithic sandwiches because the profiles were not considered. The measurements of both series and the H-sections used to join the sandwiches are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Dimensions of test specimens

Test series	Foam thickness [mm]	Overall thickness [mm]	Width [mm]	Length [mm]	H-section thickness	Overlap l [mm]
1	5	8	67,5	168	1,5	11
2	25	27	17,5	648	1,75	6

4.1.1 Testing of butt-joined sandwich structures

Within test series 1, thick and therefore stiff sandwiches with a foam core thickness of 25 mm were tested with a support span of 500 mm in four- and three-point bending. The span of the upper support in four-point bending was 250 mm. Besides the reference specimens, joint specimens with different foam cores were tested. To test these sandwiches, an Instron 5584 test machine was used. The results of these tests are shown in Fig. 3.

a.) Four-point bending

b.) Three-point bending

Figure 3: Max. load of test series 1 (foam core thickness 15 mm). a.) Four-point bending b.) Three-point bending

In both bending tests, the reference specimens failed due to indentation of the upper sheet. This is a commonly known failure behavior for sandwich structures. The difference between four-point bending and three-point bending can be explained by the difference in load application. In four-point bending, the load is applied at two points and therefore, the maximum load is much higher.

In four-point bending, the joined sandwiches differ in their failure mode depending on the foam core. The sandwiches with the core of higher density (Airex T90.150) show a failure of the joint, while the sandwiches with the foam core Airex T90.60 show no differences compared to the reference specimens. The failure modes are given in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Fracture patterns of joined sandwich structures in the case of four-point bending
a.) Failure of joint; b.) Failure due to indentation

In the case of the joined sandwiches with foam core Airex T90.150 a decrease of the bending strength of approximately 20 % is observed. The failure occurs due to a shear failure of the joint between the H-section and the lower face of the sandwich. The second core used in this study (Airex T90.60) has a density that is three times lower than that of Airex T90.150. The compressive strength is approximately three times lower, as well. Therefore, the failure occurs simultaneously with the reference specimen by indentation of the upper face sheets. This results in no changes in the maximum load. The joint does not fail and therefore, an evaluation of the joint strength is not possible.

In three-point bending, differences in the failure modes of the joint structures and the monolithic sandwiches can be observed. In the case of joint sandwiches, the joints can be identified as the weak points and the failure occurs at the joint between H-section and lower face sheet independent of the core. The H-section protects the upper face sheet from indentation in the case of the weaker foam core. As a result, a decrease of the maximum load of approximately 20 % in the case of Airex T90.150 and 10 % in the case of T90.60 can be shown, compared to the reference specimen.

From this test series, it becomes obvious that four-point bending is not suited to test sandwich structures. An evaluation of the joint design is only possible in certain cases and depends strongly on the configuration of the sandwich. Three-point bending seems to be the better choice, as in all tested cases the failure occurred in the joining area. However, it has to be considered that the overlap length was small compared to the thickness of the sandwiches and therefore the joint was quite weak.

In contrast to the specimens of series 1, the foam thickness was reduced to 5 mm for test series 2. Due to the resulting reduction of the overall thickness of the sandwiches, the support span of the lower supports was changed to 100 mm. Furthermore, the overlap length was increased to 11 mm. To test these sandwiches, an Instron 5567 test machine was used. The results for three-point bending are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Max. load of test series 2 in three-point bending

The resulting maximum loads for the specimens with the foam core made of Airex T90.150 resemble those obtained in series 1. Again, the reference specimens bear the highest load. Failure emerges due to indentation in the upper surface (Fig. 6 left). The joined sandwiches with the foam core T90.150 show a reduction in the maximum load of approximately 20 %. In this case, the failure modes of all joined sandwiches differ from the results obtained from bending in series 1. The specimens fail due to buckling close to the joining area (Fig. 6 right).

Figure 6: Failure modes of monolithic sandwich (left) and joined sandwich (right)

The H-section protects the sandwich from indentation and stiffens the whole structure. As a result, the sandwich cannot deform in this region. This effect can also be seen from the slope of the load deflection curve. The slope increases slightly by 5 %. While the deflection is increased, the deformation of the sandwich close to the joint is higher leading to buckling in this area.

In the case of the foam core with the lower density, no buckling is observed and the maximum load is nearly identical to those of the reference specimens. However, the failure mode changes again. While the reference specimens fail due to indentation, the joined sandwiches are deformed close to the joining area leading to a compression of the foam core without buckling.

4.1.4 Conclusion for testing butt-jointed sandwich structures

Within the tests shown above it is demonstrated that general statements concerning the suitability of standard tests for joined sandwich structures cannot be made. The foam core was found to be the major influence on the failure behavior. As the failure modes change, an evaluation of the joint quality has to be carried out carefully. An adaption of standardized bending tests to qualify sandwich joints can be useful, but the failure modes as well as the materials used have to be considered. A transfer of a joint design from one sandwich configuration to another is not possible, as the failure mode might differ and the load capacity cannot be guaranteed.

4.2 Testing of corner joints and T-joints

As there are no standardized test methods for corner-joints, three different fixtures were considered within this study and their influence on the test results was determined. In all cases, the specimens were clamped to a vertical beam. The load was applied parallel to the fixed sandwich beam. Sketches of these fixtures are given in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Failure modes of monolithic sandwich (left) and joined sandwich (right)

Fixture 1 uses two clamps, one at the end of one of the joined sandwich beams and the other one close to the joining area. Fixture 3 uses only one clamp at the end of the sandwich beams. In both cases, spacers with the same thickness as the angle sections (5 mm) were used. Therefore, the joining

area supports itself on the beam. Fixture 2 uses a spacer with a thickness that is three times higher. Therefore the specimens hang freely at the beginning of the testing. The influence of the fixtures on the test results was evaluated by performing tests in an Instron 5584. The tests were performed with a constant test speed of 10 mm/min. An example of the influence of the fixture method on the test results is given in Fig.8.

Figure 8: Influence of fixture method on test results

Fixture 1 results in a heavy increase of the load-deflection curve. This is caused by the lower clamp as it prevents the vertical sandwich beam from deforming. The joining area is pushed against the fixture beam, and only the horizontal sandwich beam deforms. Therefore, the deflection of the joining area is limited causing a maximum load of approximately 600 N. Fixtures 2 and 3 give nearly identical maximum loads of 450 N. However, these curves differ significantly in the deflection. While fixture 3 results in an immediate increase of the load, fixture 2 leads to a significantly lower slope followed by a plateau, where the load remains nearly constant. After this plateau, the slope increases. This behavior is caused by the free deformation. A significant increase of the load appears when the joint hits the fixture beam. Therefore, fixture 3 was chosen for further studies. Within these studies, it was shown that again the density of the foam core has a major influence on the failure behavior. While corner joints with high density failed within the joining area due to failure of the core, joints with weak foam cores tend to buckle close to joining area. An example of this fracture pattern is given in Fig. 9.

a.)

b.)

Figure 9: Influence of foam core on failure behavior: a.) Core failure in cases of foam core Airex T90.100; b.) Buckling in the case of foam core Airex T90.60

4.1.4 Conclusion

From the experiments conducted it can be seen that an evaluation of adhesively bonded sandwiches

is a demanding task, as the test requirements as well as the materials used influence the results enormously. As shown, it is possible to determine the influence of certain joints on the failure behavior and even a statement concerning the actual strength of the joint can be made.

Butt-joined sandwich structures can be tested in three-point bending and four-point bending, but the results have to be handled carefully. Within this study it is shown that the failure mode changes if joined sandwiches are tested and that a failure of the sandwich structure may not appear in the joining area but close to it. The failure mode is furthermore influenced by the sandwich design and therefore an evaluation can only be made with respect to materials of the sandwich.

As the failure in T-joints and corner joints occurs in the region of the joints, the used test techniques seem to be adequate to test the joints. However, the failure mode has to be considered as well to prevent a misinterpretation of the results.

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